

The Green Synthesis AgNPs from Basil Leaf Extract

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Abstract : Bioreduction of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) from silver ions (Ag⁺) using water extract of Thai basil leaf was successfully carried out. The basil leaf extract provided a reducing agent and stabilizing agent for a synthesis of metal nanoparticles. Silver nanoparticles received from cut and uncut basil leaf was compared. The resulting silver nanoparticles are characterized by UV-Vis spectroscopy. The maximum intensities of silver nanoparticle from cut and uncut basil leaf were 410 and 420, respectively. The techniques involved are simple, eco-friendly and rapid.

Keywords : basil leaves, silver nanoparticles, green synthesis, plant extract

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